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Results from muon reconstruction performance with ATLAS on Run-3 data

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Abstract

This note presents the first momentum performance results for the muon reconstruction, identification and isolation efficiencies of the ATLAS detector in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV using data collected in 2022 during Run-3 of the LHC. An overview of the algorithms and criteria for reconstruction and identification in $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ resonances is discussed and their efficiencies are evaluated, as well as momentum scale and resolution. The obtained results are used to improve the simulation to data agreement leading to good performances.

1 Introduction

Muon reconstruction plays a crucial role in LHC data analysis, since muons are key ingredients of many physics analyses. Innovations developed during the last years lead to several improvements e.g. in the background rejection and in the treatment of the detector geometry. These innovations improved the efficiency and momentum measurement performance. In this document, section 2 briefly describes the ATLAS detector, section 3 summarises the muon reconstruction, selection and efficiency. Finally, section 4 provides an overview of the muon momentum calibration and performance.

2 The ATLAS detector

The ATLAS detector [1] is a multipurpose particle detector with a forward–backward symmetric cylindrical geometry¹. It consists of an Inner Detector (ID), electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters, and a Muon Spectrometer (MS). In Run-3, the experimental setup has undergone enhancements through the replacement of the Small Wheel by the New Small Wheel (NSW) and the implementation of updates in the muon trigger systems [2]. The ID system is a track charged particle detector for $|\eta| < 2.5$ using a 2 T solenoid magnetic field. The MS [3] is a muon tracking detector for $|\eta| < 2.7$ with a toroidal magnetic field made of precision and trigger chambers. The field integral of the toroids ranges between 2.0 and 6.0 Tm across most of the detector. The ATLAS dataset of pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV in 2022 comprises an integrated delivered luminosity of $\approx 38.5 \text{ fb}^{-1}$.

3 Muon Reconstruction and Selection

Muons are identified and reconstructed by combining the ID and MS information. About 96% of muons are reconstructed by fitting hits from ID and MS tracks. The remainder are formed by tagging ID tracks with muon signatures in the calorimeter or the MS. The following muon types are obtained: Combined, Segment-tagged, Stand-alone and Calorimeter-tagged muons as shown in Fig. 1.

After reconstruction, muon candidates are selected by a set of requirements on the number of hits in the ID sub-detectors and MS stations as well as the track fit properties. Three working points (WP) are defined according to purity level and kinematics. The *Loose* WP provides High efficiency but less purity and larger systematics. The *Medium* WP provides a suitable efficiency and purity with low systematics. The *Tight* WP provides the highest purity with an improved background rejection at the cost of a few percent efficiency loss.

The muon isolation is either track-based or calorimeter-based and defined as the transverse energy (or momentum if considering only tracks) reconstructed in a cone around a muon and divided by the muon transverse momentum (p_T). Several WPs are defined combining track-based and calorimeter-based isolation resulting in better performance. Some of these WPs use a

Figure 1: Muon reconstruction types.

¹ATLAS uses a right-handed coordinate system with its origin at the nominal interaction point (IP) in the centre of the detector and the z -axis along the beam pipe. The x -axis points from the IP to the centre of the LHC ring, and the y -axis points upwards. Cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ) are used in the transverse plane, ϕ being the azimuthal angle around the z -axis. The pseudorapidity is defined in terms of the polar angle θ as $\eta = -\ln \tan(\theta/2)$. Angular distance is measured in units of $\Delta R = \sqrt{(\Delta\eta)^2 + (\Delta\phi)^2}$

particle-flow based algorithm² to evaluate the neutral component of the energy deposit [4]. To determine the efficiency of a certain algorithm in both data and simulation the *Tag-and-Probe* method was applied to $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ described in [4]. The deviation of the simulation from the detector behaviour in data is estimated by a Scale Factor (efficiencies ratio) that is used to correct the simulation.

Figure 2 shows the muon reconstruction and identification efficiency for $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ (Fig. 2a) as a function of η and p_T of the muon and for $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ (Fig. 2b) as a function of φ and η . For isolation efficiency, results are shown in Figure 3 for $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ as a function of muon p_T for Tight (Fig. 3a) and PflowTight (Fig. 3b) quality criteria. The ratio between data and simulation efficiencies provides scale factors with a per mil level precision with statistical (blue) and the combination of statistical and systematic uncertainties (yellow). Systematic uncertainties include possible biases introduced by the measurement method and uncertainties in the background estimation as described in [4].

(a) $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ as a function of η and p_T of the muon.

(b) $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ as a function of φ and η .

Figure 2: Muon reconstruction and identification efficiency [5].

(a) Tight muon quality.

(b) PflowTight quality criteria.

Figure 3: Muon isolation efficiency measured in $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ events [5].

4 Momentum scale and resolution

To enhance the data-to-simulation agreement the corrections described in [6] are applied to both data and MC. The data is corrected for potential charge-dependent momentum biases related to the knowledge of the detector geometry, using the $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ resonance. On the other hand, the muon momentum scale and resolution are measured using samples of $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ events. A calibration procedure is defined and applied to simulated data to match the performance measured in real data.

The invariant mass distributions for the $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ candidates are shown in Figure 4 and compared with corrected simulation that agrees with the data within the systematic

²The particle-flow-based isolation variable is defined as the sum of track-based isolation, chosen in the configuration with different cone sizes and the transverse energy of neutral particle-flow objects around the muon.

uncertainties, showing the efficiency of the p_T calibration. The band in the lower panel represents the effect of the systematic uncertainties on the MC momentum corrections. For the mean (Fig. 5a), the agreement between data and simulation is within 0.5% and the relative resolution (Fig. 5b) measured in data is approximately proportional to the average momentum of the muons. The lower panels show the data/MC ratio where the systematic uncertainties (filled area) are derived from $\pm 1\sigma$ variations of the smearing and scale parameters used to derive the correction [6].

Figure 4: Dimuon invariant mass distribution reconstructed with CB muons for (a) $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and (b) $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ [7].

(a) Fitted mean mass of the dimuon system for $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ decay as a function of the leading muon pseudorapidity.

(b) Dimuon invariant mass resolution divided by the particle's mass for CB muons in $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu\mu$ and $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ as a function of the average transverse momentum $\langle p_T \rangle$.

Figure 5: Performance plots [7].

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